

INFLUENCE OF DIFFERENT FERTILIZERS/ MANURES ON THE INCIDENCE OF MAJOR INSECT PESTS IN CHILLI

¹*Khadse Sachin Ramesh, ²N. S. Bhadauria, ³S.P.S. Tomar, ⁴Pradyuman Singh, and ⁵B. Sundar¹Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Entomology, College of Agriculture, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, India, srkhadse4@gmail.com²Professor, Department of Entomology, College of Agriculture, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, India, nareshsinghbhadauria@gmail.com³Senior Scientist, Department of Entomology, Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Gwalior, Madhya Pradesh, India, sattvam_68@yahoo.co.in⁴Scientist Entomology, B.M. College of Agriculture, Khandwa, Madhya Pradesh, India, pradyumn.singh1@gmail.com⁵Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Entomology, JNKVV, Jabalpur, Madhya Pradesh-482004, India, borkarsundar@gmail.com
srkhadse4@gmail.com

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Abstract:

Experiments were conducted during Rabi 2018-19 and 2019-20 at Entomology Research Farm, RVSKVV, College of Agriculture, Gwalior (M.P.). There were 11 treatments combination of fertilizers/ manures and along with one untreated control. It was noticed that by applying 50% RDF + neem cake @ 250 kg/ ha reduces aphid infestation significantly over control and 100% RDF. Application of neem cake @250 kg/ ha reduced the aphid population significantly over control. During present investigation it was noticed that there were no significant reduction in aphid population by increasing 25% K + reducing 50% N of RDF and by only increasing 25% K without reducing N level of recommended dose. Significantly less aphid population in the plot receiving high PK (25% RDPK) + low N (50% RDN) indicate that application of higher dose of P and K and 50% low dose of N induce the resistance against aphid. Significantly less aphid population in the plot receiving application of vermicompost @ 2.5 t/ ha showed their effectiveness in reducing the aphid infestation over control. During present investigation it was noticed that by applying 50% RDF + neem cake @ 250 kg/ ha reduces thrips infestation significantly over control and 100% RDF. Application of neem cake @250 kg/ ha reduced the thrips population significantly over control. During present investigation it was noticed that by increasing 25% K + reducing 50% N of RDF and by only increasing 25% K without reducing N level of recommended dose there were significant reduction in thrips population. Significantly less thrips population in the plot receiving high PK (25% RDPK) + low N (50% RDN) indicate that application of higher dose of P and K and 50% low dose of N induce the resistance against thrips. Significantly less thrips population in the plot receiving application of vermicompost @ 2.5 t/ ha showed their effectiveness in reducing the thrips infestation over control. Maximum fruit yield (1176 kg per ha) was recorded in [High N (25% RDN) + P+ K] followed by recommended dose of fertilizer @ 120:80:80 kg NPK/ ha (1146 kg per ha) and [High K (25% RDK) + N + P] (1143 kg per ha).

Key words: Nutrition, fertilizers, manures, aphid, thrips, chilli**Introduction**

Chilli (*Capsicum annum* L.) belongs to the family Solanaceae is an important spice cum vegetable crop commonly used in Indian dietary. It is grown throughout the year as a cash crop and used in green and red ripe dried stage for their pungency, colour and other ingredients in all culinary preparations of rich and poor alike to impart taste, flavour and colour. Nutritionally, it is a rich source of vitamin A, B and C. Capsaicin an alkaloid responsible for pungency in chillies has medicinal properties and it prevents heart attack by dilating the blood vessels (Gill, 1989). In India, chilli occupies an area of 6.84 lakh ha with annual production of 19.31 lakh tonnes and productivity of 2490 kg per ha (Anonymous, 2020a). In Andhra Pradesh, chilli occupies an area of 1.43 lakh ha with annual production of 6.60 lakh tonnes and with highest productivity of 4615 kg per ha whereas, in Madhya Pradesh, chilli occupies an area of 0.88 lakh ha with annual production of 2.18 lakh tonnes and productivity of 2488 kg per ha (Anonymous, 2020b).

Various factors are responsible for low productivity and production of chilli that include adverse climate, poor quality seeds, diseases, insect and mite pests. The insects and mites are of prime importance which significantly affects both the quality and production of chilli. About 51 insects and 2 mite species, belonging to 27 families and 9 orders were found infesting chilli (Reddy and Puttaswami, 1988). Among these thrips, *Scirtothrips dorsalis* Hood, whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* Genn., aphid, *Aphis gossypii* Glover, jassid, *Amrasca biguttula biguttula* (Ishida), fruit borer, *Helicoverpa armigra* (Hubner) and mites, *Polyphagotarsonemus latus* Banks are important pests contributing 60 to 75 per cent yield loss in green chilli. However, reports on vector transmission of leaf curl are quite contradictory because of complexities and several types of chilli viruses (Ravi, 1991), though recent information indicated significant role of viruses transmitted by aphids, whiteflies besides direct damage by thrips and mites feeding (Giraddi and Verghese, 2007).

In the last few decades, awareness of health consciousness lead to organically produced food stuffs. The tremendous demand for organically produced food has lead to the creation of new export avenues for developing countries. Organic farming is a holistic production management system which involves the use of organic manures, botanical pesticides and biological pest control strategies which can act as an alternative to the costlier, non-eco-friendly and energy intensive chemical inputs. Fertilizer application change the proportion of nutrient composition in plant tissues and consequently their nutritive value helps in the management of sucking pests (Wooldridge and Harrison, 1968). Keeping these points in view in the present field experiment was conducted to evaluate the effect of fertilizers/ manures on the population of aphid and thrips in chilli crops.

Material and methods

The research work was carried out at department of entomology, research farm, RVSKVV, Gwalior (M.P.) during Rabi 2018-19 and 2019-20. Experiment were laid out in a simple randomized block design with 12 treatments (as given in table 1) replicated three times. The crop was raised as per the recommended package of practices except for plant protection measures. All the organic manures were incorporated as a basal dose at the time of transplanting of chilli seedlings. Full dose of phosphatic and potashic fertilizers were applied before transplanting as basal, while doses of nitrogenous fertilizers were applied in two splits i.e., half dose at the time of just before transplanting and remaining half dose at three weeks after transplanting.

Observations on population of aphid and thrips were recorded in the morning hour at weekly interval starting immediately after transplanting and continued till last picking of fruits. Data was recorded on ten plants selected randomly from central rows / plot. The population of aphid was recorded by counting both nymphs and adults. In the initial stage of the crop, counting of aphid was done on whole plant and in later stage on six leaves, two each from i.e. top,

middle and bottom of each plant. The population of thrips was recorded from 10 cm twig of plants by shaking plant on white paper fixed on cardboard (20 cm x 20 cm) at weekly interval on randomly selected plants.

Result and Discussion

Aphid, *Aphis gossypii* (Glover)

On the basis of average of sixteen observations recorded during *Rabi* 2018-19 significant differences were observed in aphid population among different treatments. Minimum aphid population (8.40) was recorded in T₃ (50% RDF + neem cake - 250 kg/ ha) which found significantly less than rest of treatments except T₁₁, T₆, T₇, T₈ and T₁₀. Maximum and significantly highest population of aphid (22.03) was recorded in T₁₂ (Untreated control - No fertilizers) than rest of treatments receiving application of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers. The aphid population (15.39) recorded in T₉ [High N (25% RDN) + P+ K] was significantly higher than rest of the plots receiving organic manures or inorganic fertilizers except T₁, T₂ and T₄ but was less than control.

On the basis of average of fifteen observations recorded during *Rabi* 2019-20 showed significant differences in aphid population among different treatments. Minimum aphid population (8.38) was recorded in T₃ (50% RDF + neem cake - 250 kg/ ha) which found significantly less than rest of treatments except T₁₁, T₆, T₇, T₈, T₁₀ and T₅. Maximum and significantly highest population of aphid (20.33) was recorded in T₁₂ (Untreated control - No fertilizers) than rest of treatments receiving application of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers. The aphid population (14.46) recorded in T₉ [High N (25% RDN) + P+ K] was significantly higher than rest of the plots receiving organic manures or inorganic fertilizers except T₁, T₂ and T₄ but was less than control.

Mean aphid population

On the basis of average of two years (*Rabi* 2018-19 and 2019-20) data significant differences were observed in aphid population among different treatments. Minimum aphid population (8.39) was recorded in T₃ (50% RDF + neem cake - 250 kg/ ha) which found significantly less than rest of treatments except T₁₁, T₆, T₇, T₈ and T₁₀. Whereas maximum and significantly highest population of aphid (21.18) was recorded in T₁₂ (Untreated control - No fertilizers) than all the treatments receiving application of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers. The aphid population (14.93) recorded in T₉ [High N (25% RDN) + P+ K] was significantly higher than the population in rest of the plots receiving organic manures or inorganic fertilizers except T₁, T₂ and T₄.

During present investigation it was noticed that by applying 50% RDF + neem cake @250 kg/ ha reduces aphid infestation significantly over control and 100% RDF. Application of neem cake @250 kg/ ha reduced the aphid population significantly over control. Similar to present finding Naik *et al.* (2009) also reported significantly lower aphid population by application of neem cake in cotton crop. During present investigation it was noticed that there were no significant reduction in aphid population by increasing 25% K + reducing 50% N of RDF and by only increasing 25% K without reducing N level of recommended dose. Significantly less aphid population in the plot receiving high PK (25% RDPK) + low N (50% RDN) indicate that application of higher dose of P and K and 50% low dose of N induce the resistance against aphid. Significantly less aphid population in the plot receiving application of vermicompost @ 2.5 t/ ha showed their effectiveness in reducing the aphid infestation over control. Balakrishnan *et al.* (2005) and Naik *et al.* (2009) reported vermicompost to be effective in reducing the aphid population on cotton crop also in agreement with the present results.

Thrips, *Scirtothrips dorsalis* (Hood)

On the basis of average of sixteen observations recorded during *Rabi* 2018-19 showed significant differences in thrips population among different treatments. Minimum thrips population (10.86) was recorded in T₃ (50% RDF + neem cake - 250 kg/ ha) which found significantly less than rest of treatments except T₇, T₆, T₁₁ and T₈. Maximum and significantly highest population of thrips (26.52) was recorded in T₁₂ (Untreated control - No fertilizers) than rest of treatments receiving application of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers except T₉. The thrips population (22.31) recorded in T₉ [High N (25% RDN) + P+ K] was significantly higher than rest of the plots receiving organic manures or inorganic fertilizers except T₁, T₁₀, T₂ and T₄ and control.

On the basis of average of sixteen observations recorded on thrips population during *Rabi* 2019-20 showed significant differences among different treatments. Minimum thrips population (9.18) was recorded in T₃ (50% RDF + neem cake - 250 kg/ ha) which found significantly less than rest of treatments except T₇, T₆ and T₁₁. Whereas maximum and significantly highest population of thrips (23.66) was recorded in T₁₂ (Untreated control - No fertilizers) than rest of treatments receiving application of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers except T₉. The thrips population (20.03) recorded in T₉ [High N (25% RDN) + P+ K] was significantly higher than rest of the plots receiving organic manures or inorganic fertilizers except T₁, T₁₀, T₂, T₄ and control.

Mean thrips population

On the basis of average of two years (*Rabi* 2018-19 and 2019-20) data significant differences were observed in thrips population among different treatments. Minimum thrips population (10.02) was recorded in T₃ (50% RDF + neem cake - 250 kg/ ha) which found significantly less than rest of treatments except T₇, T₆ and T₁₁. Whereas maximum and significantly highest population of thrips (25.09) was recorded in T₁₂ (Untreated control - No fertilizers) than all the treatments receiving application of organic manures and inorganic fertilizers except T₉. The thrips population (21.17) recorded in T₉ [High N (25% RDN) + P+ K] was significantly higher than the population in rest of the plots receiving organic manures or inorganic fertilizers except T₁, T₁₀, T₂, T₄ and control.

During present investigation it was noticed that by applying 50% RDF + neem cake @250 kg/ ha reduces thrips infestation significantly over control and 100% RDF. Giraddi and Verghese (2007) reported that combined applications of neem cake @250 kg/ha with 50% RDF significantly lowered thrips population support the present finding. Application of neem cake @250 kg/ ha reduced the thrips population significantly over control. During present investigation it was noticed that by increasing 25% K + reducing 50% N of RDF and by only increasing 25% K without reducing N level of recommended dose there were significant reduction in thrips population. Significantly less thrips population in the plot receiving high PK (25% RDPK) + low N (50% RDN) indicate that application of higher dose of P and K and 50% low dose of N induce the resistance against thrips. Significantly less thrips population in the plot receiving application of vermicompost @ 2.5 t/ ha showed their effectiveness in reducing the thrips infestation over control. Giraddi and Verghese (2007) reported that vermicompost (@1500 kg/ha + 50% RDF) to be effective in reducing the thrips population on chilli also in line with the present results. Present findings are deviating from the findings of Gayathri Devi (2006) who reported that significantly highest population was recorded in vermicompost 1.25 t/ha + neem cake 0.25 t/ha + 0% recommended N.

Table 1: Influence of different doses of fertilizers/ manures on incidence of aphids (*Aphis gossypii* Glover) and thrips (*Scirtothrips dorsalis* Hood) in chilli

T	Treatments details	No. of aphid/ 6 leaves/ plant			No. of thrips/ 10 cm twig/ plant		
		2018-19	2019-20	Average	2018-19	2019-20	Average
T ₁	Recommended dose of fertilizer (120:80:80 kg NPK / ha)	13.15 (3.69)	12.64 (3.61)	12.90 (3.65)	20.24 (4.54)	18.09 (4.30)	19.17 (4.42)
T ₂	50% RDF + vermicompost (1.25 t / ha)	12.78 (3.64)	12.34 (3.57)	12.56 (3.61)	18.11 (4.30)	16.14 (4.07)	17.12 (4.19)
T ₃	50% RDF + neem cake (250 kg / ha)	8.40 (2.98)	8.38 (2.97)	8.39 (2.97)	10.86 (3.36)	9.18 (3.10)	10.02 (3.24)
T ₄	Vermicompost (2.5 t / ha)	12.31 (3.58)	11.85 (3.51)	12.08 (3.54)	17.30 (4.22)	15.26 (3.97)	16.28 (4.09)
T ₅	Neem cake (250 kg / ha)	11.67 (3.49)	11.19 (3.41)	11.43 (3.45)	15.94 (4.05)	14.04 (3.81)	14.99 (3.93)
T ₆	Vermicompost (2.5 t / ha) + Neem cake (250 kg / ha)	9.23 (3.12)	9.09 (3.10)	9.16 (3.10)	12.88 (3.65)	11.06 (3.39)	11.97 (3.53)
T ₇	High K (25% RDK) + low N (50% RDN) + P	9.96 (3.23)	9.74 (3.20)	9.85 (3.22)	11.72 (3.49)	9.97 (3.23)	10.84 (3.36)
T ₈	High K (25% RDK) + N + P	10.45 (3.31)	10.19 (3.26)	10.32 (3.28)	15.12 (3.94)	13.23 (3.69)	14.17 (3.82)
T ₉	High N (25% RDN) + P+ K	15.39 (3.99)	14.46 (3.86)	14.93 (3.92)	22.31 (4.77)	20.03 (4.52)	21.17 (4.65)
T ₁₀	Low N (50% RDN) + P + K	11.16 (3.41)	10.80 (3.36)	10.98 (3.38)	19.32 (4.44)	17.22 (4.20)	18.27 (4.32)
T ₁₁	High PK (25% RDPK) + Low N (50% RDN)	8.90 (3.07)	8.66 (3.01)	8.78 (3.04)	13.74 (3.76)	11.95 (3.52)	12.84 (3.64)
T ₁₂	Untreated control (No fertilizers)	22.03 (4.75)	20.33 (4.55)	21.18 (4.64)	26.52 (5.18)	23.66 (4.90)	25.09 (5.04)
	S.Em.±	(0.16)	(0.16)	(0.15)	(0.20)	(0.19)	(0.19)
	C.D. at 5 %	(0.46)	(0.47)	(0.45)	(0.58)	(0.57)	(0.57)

Figures in the parentheses are square root transformed values

Conclusion:

Based on the results of investigation, it can be concluded that minimum aphid population was recorded in 50% RDF + neem cake @250 kg/ ha followed by [High PK (25% RDPK) + Low N (50% RDN)] and vermicompost @2.5 t/ ha + neem cake @250 kg/ ha. Minimum thrips population was recorded in 50% RDF + neem cake @250 kg/ ha followed by [High K (25% RDK) + low N (50% RDN) + P] and vermicompost @2.5 t/ ha + neem cake @250 kg/ ha. Application of neem cake @250 kg/ ha reduced the aphid and thrips population significantly over control. During present investigation it was noticed that there were no significant reduction in aphid population by increasing 25% K + reducing 50% N of RDF and by only increasing 25% K without reducing N level of recommended dose, whereas there were significant reduction in thrips population. Significantly less aphid and thrips population in the plot receiving high PK (25% RDPK) + low N (50% RDN) indicate that application of higher dose of P and K and 50% low dose of N induce the resistance against aphid and thrips. Maximum fruit yield was recorded in [High N (25% RDN) + P+ K] followed by recommended dose of fertilizer @120:80:80 kg NPK/ ha and [High K (25% RDK) + N + P]

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